

Deadjectival Nominalizations in Balinese

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to know the formation of nouns through adjective word classes and the meaning of affixes attached to adjective base words to form new nouns. The data source of this research is taken from written sources in the form of storybooks (*Satua Bali*). Data collection uses the listening method and note-taking technique. In this case, the researcher listens by reading the sourcebook. Looking for clauses that contain nouns. All collected data were identified and then classified the data. After the data is collected, it is analyzed. Then the stage of analysis or discussion of research results is carried out. The data that has been obtained in the data collection process is analyzed based on the group of problems discussed in the study. The method used in data analysis is using the mark reading technique. This technique is used to determine nouns derived from adjectives in the clause structure. Then, the analysis is carried out by the formulation of the problem, namely analyzing the morphological process of adjectives into nouns, as well as the semantic structure of Balinese noun deadjectives. Furthermore, the parsing technique is used, namely by describing the noun to find out the basic form and the affixes attached to it. This research uses the theory of morphology by Katamba and Stonham in 2006. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the nominalization process is derived from adjectives through limited affixation strategies, including prefixes, confixes, and combinations. Prefixes and their semantic meanings include {{pa-}'something/thing that makes', {su-}'too', {paN-}'tool', most', and 'cause'. Confixes include {ke-an} and {pa-an} semantically meaning 'result'. Combifixes include {pi-an}, and {ka-an} semantically meaning 'flavor'.

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1. Introduction

In the last few decades, there have been many studies related to the Balinese language. For example, in terms of the word formation process (affixation) (see Bawa and Jendra, 1981; Denes et al, 1991; Simpen 2008; Suandi, 2008; Sugata, 2019), its syntactic structure (see Bawa et al, 1983; Sudjiati, 2003; Arka, 2003; Artawa, 2013; Trisnawati, (2015)). However, there is still very little research on Balinese nominalization. To nominalization, research is no less important to be researched because the use of nouns in communication is needed. In a sentence, nouns are the main word class besides verbs. Nominalization is an important concept in linguistic studies because nominalization is the process of turning words other than nouns into nouns (Rahert and Alexiadou, 2010; Comrie and Thompson 2007; Ha Yap, et al., 2011). The verb as the center of the clause needs an argument with a noun word class. Word class changes from other word classes to nouns are required by language speakers to organize lingual constructions. For example, an adjective becomes a noun. Based on this, this study is very important, because the nominalization process of each language has morphological and syntactic characteristics, so the results of the study will be theoretical input across languages.

Research related to Balinese adjectives itself has been conducted by Budiarta (2017) and Budiasa (2015). Budiarta in his article entitled 'Balinese Adjectives' reveals the uniqueness of the grammatical behavior of adjectives in Balinese. Based on Dixon's (2010) Basic Grammatical Theory framework, Balinese adjectives have similar grammatical behavior as other word classes, such as verbs and nouns. The oral data of five Balinese native speakers shows that Balinese adjectives can be combined with nouns to form noun phrases, which function as modifiers. Six affixes that cause changes in grammatical behavior. These affixes are: (1) the suffix -ang, (2) a combination of suffixes -ang and -a, (3) the suffix -in, (4) a combination of suffixes -in and -a, (5) the suffix -an, and (6) confix ng-ang. Aspect, tense, and mode can be attached to Balinese adjectives, and Balinese adjectives are a word class that can only form comparative structures. Budiasa (2015) examined adjective synonymy in Balinese. The purpose is to describe the number of synonym pairs that can be analyzed and the meaning relationship of adjectives that become synonym pairs in Balinese. Data acquisition in the field is done by listening to the use of Balinese, both in written and spoken form. Based on the data analysis, it is found that the nature of adjective-adjective synonym pairs in Balinese is influenced by several factors, such as variety, speech level, and taste value. Two synonyms are never found to have absolute similarity in meaning.

As a lexical unit, each word has different semantic relations in building sentence structures. The difference causes a word does not have the same possibility to coexist with other words in one sentence building. The two linguists mentioned above provide enough knowledge about the behavior of adjectives in Balinese itself. However, nominalization derived from adjectives is not touched upon. Even so, there are studies on Balinese nominalization that have discussed it. Although there are still very few found. Related studies include Balinese noun morphology researched by Denes et al (1991). Denes et al. examined the formation of Balinese nouns based on a structural theoretical framework. They studied the morphemic process of Balinese nouns concerning the addition of prefixes, infixes, and suffixes, and the possibility of combining the three with their confixes, as well as knowing more about the meaning and function of the morphological process. The result of affixation is derivational or just a paradigmatic process.

Discuss the semantic aspects of the morphemic process. Denes et al. emphasized that the formation of complex nouns can be done in several ways: a) combining the base morpheme with the base morpheme; b) adding affixes (prefixes, suffixes, and certain confixes) to the base morpheme; c) fusion, both endocentric and exocentric. The morphological structure of Balinese nouns undergoes a morphophonological process, which summarizes the addition, removal, and shifting of certain

phonemes in the base form. The description of Balinese noun forms is based on syntactic and morphological distribution, both for single or free morphemes and for complex forms. In complex forms, certain affixes are involved in the noun formation process. For example, prefixes {paN-an}, which are attached to base morphemes and free morphemes; confixes {pa-an} and {ka-an} which are attached to base morphemes derived from adjectives, verbs, and numbers.

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Data acquisition in the field is done by listening to the use of Balinese, both in written and spoken form. Based on the data analysis, it is found that the nature of adjective-adjective synonym pairs in Balinese is influenced by several factors, such as variety, speech level, and taste value. Two synonyms are never found to have absolute similarity in meaning. As a lexical unit, each word has different semantic relations in building sentence structures. The difference causes a word does not have the same possibility to coexist with other words in one sentence building. The two linguists mentioned above provide enough knowledge about the behavior of adjectives in Balinese itself. However, nominalization derived from adjectives is not touched upon. Even so, there are studies on Balinese nominalization that have discussed it. Although there are still very few found. Related studies include Balinese noun morphology researched by Denes et al (1991).

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adjective + adjective, adjective + precatatorial. There are several kinds of nouns formed from the repetition of language units, namely: (1) repetition of the first syllable in the lexeme with weakening of vowel phonemes; (2) repetition of language units or lexemes as a whole; (3) nouns formed by combining lexemes with other lexemes into noun phrases. The lexemes forming the noun phrase can be a combination of noun + noun, noun + adjective, noun + numeral, and noun + verb. There are two kinds of derived nouns formed by reducing clauses to noun phrases, namely nouns derived through relativization with *ane/sane* 'which' and nouns derived from the nominalization of the verb phrase of the clause predicate and the permutation of the nominalized verb phrase forward. In terms of the syntactic function that nouns can occupy in a sentence or clause structure, Balinese nouns can serve as subject, predicate, object, complement, and adverb. However, none of these studies discuss deadjectival nominalization. Nominalization derived from adjectives is only described by its morphophonemic process without a deeper description. The study of deadjectival nominalization is not done in depth. Therefore, the research cannot provide comprehensive information about the formation of nouns derived from adjectives.

In contrast to the above studies, this study examines nominalization specifically the nominalization process derived from adjectives. This is based on Halliday's (2004:358) statement that 'nominalization refers to the phenomenon that any element or group of elements, phrases or clauses can function as a noun structure'. This study was chosen, because the process of nominalization in each language has morphological and syntactic characteristics, so the results of the study will be theoretical input cross-linguistically. This study uses the theory of morphology according to Katamba and Stonham (2006). According to Katamba and Stonham, there are various word-building elements used to create structures, including roots, affixes, stems, and base. The root is the irreducible core of the word, nothing at all else is attached to it. It is a part that is always present, perhaps with some modifications, in the various manifestations of the lexeme. Roots that can stand on their own are called free morphemes, for example, *man*, *book*, *tea*, *sweet*, *cook*, and so on. An affix is a morpheme that only appears when attached to another morpheme or morphemes such as root stem or base. Affixes are bound morphemes. There are three types of affixes. (1) Prefixes.

Prefixes are affixes attached in front of the root or stem or base such as *re-*, *un-*, and *in-*. Examples: *re-make*, *un-kind*, *in-decent*; (2) Suffixes. Suffixes are affixes that come after the root (or stem or base) such as *-ly*, *-er*, *-ist*, *-s*, *-ing*, and *-ed*. Examples: *kind-ly*, *wait-er*, *book-s*, *walk-ed*. (3) Infixes. Infixes are affixes inserted into the root itself. English example: *{-n-}* which inserts before the last consonant of a Latin root. This infix undergoes a place of articulatory assimilation; (4) Simulfix (simultaneous affix) is an affix located only at the prefix of the root word. Simulfixes are not just affixes but enter simultaneously into the first syllable of the base word. Simulfixes are considered non-standard word formations and are commonly used in conversational or local languages. Simulfixes focus on segmental features that can change the category of a form through nasalization which functions as verb formers in conversational varieties manifested by segmental features that are fused to the base form. Derived affixes are used to create new lexemes with: (i) significantly modify the meaning of the base it is attached to, without necessarily changing its grammatical category (see *kind* and *unkind*); (ii) The affix brings about a change in the grammatical class of the base as well as a possible change in meaning (as in the case of *hard* (adjective) and *hardship* (abstract noun); or (iii) the affix can cause a shift in the grammatical sub-class of the word without moving it to a new word class (as in the case of *friend* (concrete noun) and *friendship* (abstract noun)). Derivational affixes like *un-* can change *kind* (adjective) to *un-kind* (adverb). In this case, the derivational word has the meaning of the opposite of the input. Stem is the part of the word that exists before any inflectional affixes (i.e. affixes whose presence is required by syntax such as singular and plural number markers in nouns, verb forms, and so on) are added, e.g. the noun *cats*. Noun stem: *cat* while *-s* is a plural suffix. The plural inflectional suffix *-s* is attached to the stem *cat* which is a bare root, i.e. an irreducible root. 4. The base

is also a unit to which affixes can be added. The affixes attached to the root can be either inflectional affixes chosen for syntactic reasons or derivational affixes that change the meaning or grammatical category of the base. An unadorned root like *boy* can be a base because it can have an inflectional affix like *-s* attached to it to form the plural of boys or a derivational affix like *-ish* to turn the noun *boy* into the adjective *boyish*. In other words, all roots are bases. The base is called stem only in the context of inflectional morphology.

More specifically, this research aims to find out the characteristics of language in morphology, so that the results of the research will be theoretical input cross-linguistically. In the end, the results of this study are expected to provide new references on nominalization as a development of previous Balinese studies and can provide input to linguists who pursue linguistics related to cross-language nominalization.

2. Theory and Methods

2.1 Data source

The data source of this research is taken from written sources in the form of storybooks (Satua Bali), Balinese short story collections, and Balinese newspapers (Bali Orti). Researchers use written data to make it easier to get data. This is because in written data there are various topics of stories or conversations that allow the nominalization of adjectives to appear. Written data sources are taken from Balinese stories and Balinese short story collections and the Orti Bali newspaper contained in the 2019-2022 edition of the Bali Post newspaper. In the Orti Bali newspaper, there are texts in the form of short stories and news/information that use Balinese. The reason for using Orti Bali newspaper is also to make it easier to get the desired data.

2.2 Data Collection

Data collection uses the listening method and note-taking technique. In this case, the researcher listens by reading the sourcebook. Looking for clauses that contain nouns. All collected data were identified and then classified the data by distinguishing between data and non-data. After the data is collected, it is analyzed.

2.3 Data Analysis

At this stage is the stage of analysis or discussion of research results. The data that has been obtained in the data collection process is analyzed based on the group of problems discussed in the study. The method used in data analysis is using the mark reading technique. This technique is used to determine nouns derived from adjectives in the clause structure. Then, the analysis is carried out by the formulation of the problem, namely analyzing the morphological process of adjectives into nouns, as well as the semantic structure of Balinese noun deadjectives. Furthermore, the shift technique (transposition) is used, which is a technique for changing the position of the noun to see its original form again. This transposition can change the structure of the constituent/argument or its valency.

3. Results and Discussion

The formation of nouns derived from basic lexemes categorized as adjectives, through affix attachment in the form of prefixes (*{pa-}*, *{su-}*, *{paN-}*), confixes (*{ke-an}*, *{pa-an}*) affix

combinations (*{pi-an}*, *{ka-an}*). The following nouns are derived from adjective base morphemes and their morphological formation process.

Prefix

Prefixes are affixes in the form of letters or several letters that are added to the beginning of a word to change or modify the meaning of the word. Each prefix, even though it is only a letter or group of letters, is considered to have its meaning which comes from the formation of meaning when the prefix is used with the base word that is the core. Prefixes in Balinese have several forms, among others:

Prefix {pa-}

1. Yan sida baan cai ngeretang indriya sinah sing bakal nepukin *pakeweh*.
'If can you control PRED passions OBJ, won't find PRED it difficult OBJ'
'If you can control your passions, you won't find it difficult.' (*I Tuma Teken I Titih:33*)
2. Unduke ene anggo *pabaat* keneh.
This problem SUBJ cause PRED heavy heart OBJ
'This problem is the cause of a heavy heart'. (*intuitive author:2023*)

For example, clause 1 above, the words *pakeweh* 'difficulty' and *pabaat* in clause 2 are nouns. The noun *pakeweh* comes from the root morpheme *keweh* 'difficulty' which is an adjective. Likewise, the noun *pabaat* comes from the base morpheme *baat* 'heavy' which is an adjective. The adjective *keweh* dan *baat* receives the prefix /pa-/, thus forming a new word that previously had an adjective class to become a noun class. The distribution of the prefix {pa-} can be formulated as follows.

Prefix + MDAj.....>Nomina
{pa-}+ *keweh/keweh* / 'difficult'>*pakeweh /pakeweh* / 'difficulty'
{pa-}+*baat/baat* / 'heavy'>*pabaat /pabaat* / 'burden'

The affixation attached to the adjective base morpheme has the following structure and meaning. The prefix {pa-} nominalizes the adjectival base morpheme *keweh* and expresses the meaning of 'something that makes it difficult'. In the clause structure, it functions as an object.

- Prefix {su-}

The formation of nouns derived from adjectives through the attachment of the prefix {su-}. Here is an example of the data.

3. Inget *subakti* teken Sanghyang Aswinodéwa
'Remember to bePRED devoted toPREP Sanghyang Aswinodewa'
'Remember to be devoted to Sanghyang Aswinodewa'. (*Balian Sadhu:24*)

Clause 3 above contains the word *subakti* 'love' which is a noun. The noun *subakti* comes from the free base morpheme *bakti* 'love' which is an adjective. The adjective *bakti* receives the prefix {su-} which forms the new word *subakti*. The noun *subakti* has the class of a noun. Its distribution can be formulated as follows.

prefix + MDAdj.....>Nomina
 {su-} + bakti /*bakti*/ 'devot' /> subakti /*subakti*/ 'devotion'

The prefix {*su-*} attached to the base morpheme *bakti* means 'too'.

- Prefix {*paN-*}

Nominees are also formed by adding the prefix {*paN-*} to the base morpheme derived from adjectives. Examples of data can be seen below.

4. Sebune ento tuah gook ane dalem, misi somi liu, angone *panganget*
 'The nest is just a deep hole, containing straw a lot of OBJ used for heating
 yen masan ujan.
 during the rainy season
 'The nest is just a deep hole, containing a lot of straw used for heating during the rainy season'.
(Pupulan Satua Bali:30)
5. *Panglingsir* puri Klungkung seneng melancaran.
 Elder palace Klungkung SUBJ like go around PRED
 'Klungkung palace elders love to travel'. (intuitive author: 2023)
6. Sane mangkin titian nunas *pangampura*.
 From now ISUBJ begPRED forgivenessOBJ
 'From now on I beg forgiveness'. (*Dadong Nusa:21*)

In the example clauses above, there is the word *panganget* 'warmer' in clause 4, *panglingsir* 'elder/elder' in clause 5 and *pangampura* 'apology' in clause 6. All three words are nouns. The noun *panganget* comes from the free base morpheme *anget* 'warm' which is an adjective. Likewise, the noun *panglingsir* comes from the base morpheme *lingsir* 'old/elderly' which is also an adjective. The noun *pangampura* comes from the root morpheme *ampura* 'sorry' which is an adjective. Each of them receives the prefix {*paN-*} and becomes *panganget*, *panglingsir* and *pangampura*, all of which are nouns. The distribution can be formulated as below.

prefix + MDAdj.....>Nomina
 {*paN-*}+ *anget* /*anget*/ 'warm'>*panganget* /*panganget*/ 'warmer'
 {*paN-*}+ *lingsir* /*lingsir*/ 'old'>*panglingsir* /*panglingsir*/ 'elder'
 {*paN-*}+ *ampura* /*ampura*/ 'sorry'>*pangampura* /*pangampura*/ 'apology'

In addition to the addition of phonemes, the formation of nouns derived from the basic morfem of adjectives also has the addition of phonemes as follows.

7. Anake ane tiwal janji turmaning lempas teken pasumayan, sinah
 'People SUBJ who break promises and break promises must
 nemu *panyengkala*.
 meet disaster.
 'People who break promises and break promises must meet disaster'. (*Bikul Teken Semal:20*)
8. Irika raris akeh panjak Ida Bhatara Indra sane keni panyungkan miwah padem.
 ThereSUBJ were many people of Ida Bhatara IndraPRED who got sic and died'

'There were many people of Ida Bhatara Indra who got sick and died'.

(*Pengangon Bebek:16*)

Clauses 7 and 8 above contain the words *panyengkala* 'something that causes an accident' and *panyungkan* 'something that causes pain' which are nouns. Both nouns are derived from the base morphemes *sengkala* 'bad luck/disaster/danger' and *sungkan* 'pain' which are adjectives. The two root morphemes are attached with the prefix {paN-} to form the new words *panyengkala* and *panyungkan*, which are nouns. The basic morphemes in forming nouns have the phoneme {s} at the beginning of the words *sengkala* and *sungkan* becoming {pany-}. The distribution can be formulated as follows.

prefix + MDAdj>Nomina

{paN-}+sengkala/*sengkala*/'danger'...>*panyengkala/panyengkala*/'dangerer'

{paN-}+sungkan/*sungkan*/'sick'...>*panyungkan/panyungkan*/'sickness'

The prefix {paN-} attached to the two root words means 'cause'.

Confix

Confixes. Confixes are affixes that are attached at the beginning and end of the base word. Confixes must be placed at the same time on the base (must enclose the base) because confixes are single affixes, which of course have a unified form and a unified meaning.

- Confix {ke-an}

9. Panak ento *kesugihan* ane tusing nyidayang baan nyambatang.

'The child SUBJ is wealthPRED that cannot be called'

'The child is wealth that cannot be called'. (*Bali Orti, 17 Maret 2019:7*)

10. Da ja *kesaktian* gelahang iba, ngae umah dogen iba tusing bisa.

'Don't have your powers, have you makePRED a house just you can't'

'Don't have your powers, just make a house you can't'. (*I Kedis Sangsiah Teken I Bojog:21*)

11. Yadiastun ngalih amah-amahan, *kedharman* ento sing je dadi engsapang.

Even if looking forPRED food OBJ, kindness that should not be forgotten'

'Even if you are looking for food, that kindness should not be forgotten'.

(*I Tuma Teken I Titih:33*)

In the clauses above, there are the words *kesugihan* 'wealth owned' in clause 9, *kesaktian* 'ability to do something' in clause 10, *kedharman* 'good character' in clause 11. All three words are nouns. The three nouns have free base morphemes *sugih* 'a lot of wealth or money', *sakti* 'able to do something beyond nature', and *dharmo* 'good' which are noun categories. Then each of these adjectives gets the confix {ke-an} to become *kesugihan*, *kesaktian* and *kedharman* which are noun classes. The distribution can be formulated as follows.

Confix + MDAdj>Nomina

{ke-an} +sugih/*sugih*/'rich'>*kesugihan/kesugihan*/'wealth'

{ke-an} +sakti/*sakti*/'magic'>*kesaktian/kesaktian*/'magical'

{ke-an} +dharmo/*dharmo*/'good'>*kedharman/kedharman*/'goodness'

- *Confix {pa-an}*

Nouns are also formed by attaching the suffix {pa-an} to the base morpheme which is an adjective. Here's an example. Confix {pa-an}. Nouns are also formed by attaching the suffix {pa-an} to the base morpheme which is an adjective. Here's an example.

12. Ia makeneh *papolosan* mirib baan I Mémé madan Dangin.
 'She SUBJ thinks PRED the way she does OBJ, probably because Mom is named Dangin
 'She thinks the way she does, probably because Mom is named Dangin'. (*Meme Dangin:7*)

Clause 12 above is filled with the word *papolosan* 'simplicity', which is a noun. The noun *papolosan* comes from the free base morpheme *polos* 'as it is/honest' which is an adjective. The adjective *polos* receives the suffix {pa-an}, forming the new word *papolosan*, which is also a noun. Its distribution can be formulated as follows.

. Confix + MDAj.....>Nomina
 {pa-an} + polos/*polos*/'simply'>*papolosan/papolosan*/'simplicity'
 The confix {pa-an} attached to the base morpheme /*polos*/ means 'nature'.

Combifix (Combinations Affix)

A combination of affixes is a combination of two or more affixes joined to a base form. Each of the affixes has its form and grammatical meaning, which is affixed simultaneously to the base form.

In Balinese, there are also nouns derived from a gradual affixation process called affix combination. Affix combinations are similar to confixes, but they are different. The use of confixes is done directly on the base word, while affix combinations occur gradually. Here are the data that are attached by combinations of affixes.

- *Combifiks {pi-an}*

13. Punika mawinan patut kadulurin tur kadasarin antuk *pikayunan* sane
 That's why it's good to take precedence and be based on feelings
 becik tur sumeken duaning kahanan sane jagi kapanggih nenten ja dangan.
 good and true because everyone to be found is not a danger'
 'That's why it's good to take precedence and be based on Good and true feelings because
 everyone to be found is not a danger'. (*Bali Orti:6*)

In the clause above, there is the noun *pikayunan* 'feeling, heart' in clause 13. The noun *pikayunan* comes from the free base morpheme *kayun* 'feeling, heart' which is a noun class. The noun *kayun* takes the suffix /-an/ to become *kayunan* 'feeling' which has the class of a noun. The noun *kayun* also receives the prefix {pi-} to become *pikayun*. The combination of the two affixes also forms a new noun, *pikayunan*, as in the example clause above. The process of combining the adjective *kayun* can be described as follows.

Combifiks {ka-an}

14. Tuah totonan buron tusing bisa ngalap *kapiolasan* tur *kapitresnan* anak len.
 Only that DEF animals cannot accept the kindness and love of others
 'Only that animals cannot accept the kindness and love of others'. (*I Cita Maprekara:19*)

In clause 14 above, the words *kapiolasan* 'pity' and *kapitresnan* 'affection and love' are abstract nouns. When broken down, the words *kapiolasan* and *kapitresnan* are derived from the free base morphemes *olas* 'pity' and *tresna* 'love'. The words *olas* and *tresna* are adjective class words. *Kapiolasan* and *kapitresnan* have the following affixation process. The adjective *olas* first receives the prefix {pi-} to become *piolas* 'pity'. The word *piolas* has the class of a noun. After that, the word *piolas* receives the confix {ka-an} to become *kapiolasan*.

Likewise, the noun *kapitresnan* has the following distribution.

4. Conclusions

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the nominalization process derived from adjectives through limited affixation strategies includes prefixes, confixes, and combinations. Prefixes and their semantic meanings include {pa-} 'something/thing that makes', {su-} 'too', {paN-} 'tool', 'most', and 'cause'. Confixes include {ke-an} and {pa-an} semantically meaning 'result'. Combifixes include {pi-an}, and {ka-an} semantically meaning flavor.

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References

- Alexiadou, Artemis and Rathert Monica. 2010. *The Syntax of Nominalizations Across Languages and Frameworks* (Eds). De Gruyter Mouton.
- Arka, I Wayan. 2003. *Balinese Morphosyntax: a Lexical-Functional Approach*. Pacific Linguistics. Canberra.
- Artawa, Ketut. 2013. The basic verb construction in Balinese, in Alexander Adelaar (ed.), *Voice variation in Austronesian languages of Indonesia*. NUSA 54, 5-27. [Permanent URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10108/71803>].
- Bawa, I.W. and Jendra I.W 1981. *Balinese Language Structure*. Jrootta: Center for Language Development, Ministry of Education and Culture. Jrootta.
- Bawa, et al. 1983. *Balinese Syntax*. Center for Language Development, Ministry of Education and Culture. Jrootta.
- Beratha, N.L.S. 1992. *Evolution of verbal morphology in Balinese*. PhD thesis: Australian National University, Canberra.
- Beratha, Ni Luh Sutjiati. 2012. *Ancient Balinese Phrases and their Development into Modern Balinese*. Vol.02. No. 01, October 02: *Journal of Balinese Studies*.
- Bungin, Burhan. 2001. *Qualitative Research Methodology: Methodological Actualization Towards Contemporary Variants*. Jrootta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada. Adnyana.
- Creswell, John W. 2014. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Sage Publication, Inc.
- Comrie, Bernard and Sandra Thompson. 1985/2007. *Lexical nominalization*. In Timothy Shopen (ed.), *Language typology and syntactic description*. Volume 3, 334-381. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Denes, dkk. 1991. *Morfologi Nomina bahasa Bali*. Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan. Jrootta.
- Dixon. R.M.W. 2010. *Basic Linguistic Theory: Grammatical Topics*. Volume 2: Oxford University Press Inc. New York.

- Dixon, R.M.W. 2010. *Basic Linguistic Theory; Methodology*. Volume 1: Oxford University Press Inc. New York.
- Gerner, Matthias. 2012. The Typology of Nominalization (Review article on: Foong Ha Yap, Karen Grunow-Hårsta and Janick Wrona. *Nominalization in Asian Languages: Diachronic and Typological Perspectives*. *Language and Linguistics*. http://www.ling.sinica.edu.tw/files/publication/j2012_4_07_9135.pdf
- Katamba, Francis dan Stonham, John. 2006. *Morphology*. Second Edition. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Katamba Francis. 1993. *Morphology*. St. Martin's Press. New York.
- Kroeger, R. Paul. 2005. *Analyzing Grammar: An Introduction*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lieber, Rochelle. 2004. *Morphology and Lexical Semantics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Mahsun, M.S. 2007. *Metode Penelitian Bahasa: Tahapan Strategi, Metode, dan Tekniknya*. Jrootta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Saryana, I Wayan. 2017. *Nominalisasi Bahasa Bali: Jurnal Kulturistik*
- Sudaryanto, 2015. *Metode dan Aneka Teknik Analisis Bahasa*. Yogyakarta: Sanata Dharma University Press.
- Shibatani, Masayoshi. 2017. Nominalization. In Masayoshi Shibatani, Shigeru Miyagawa, and Hashi Noda (eds.), *Handbook of Japanese syntax*. 271-332. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- Shibatani, Masayoshi. 2019. *What is nominalization? Towards The Theoretical Foundations of Nominalization*. John Benjamins Publishing Company
- Shopen, Timothy. 2007. *Language Typology and Syntactic Description*. Second Edition. Volume III: Grammatical categories and The Lexicon. Cambridge University Press. New York.
- Shopen, Timothy. 2007. *Language Typology and Syntactic Description*. Second Edition. Volume I: Clause Structure. Cambridge University Press. New York.
- Trisnawati, A.A. Ary. 2015. *Nomina Bahasa Bali Dalam Novel Tresnane Lebur Ajur Satonden Kembang: Kajian Tipologi Sintaksis: (tesis) Pascasarjana Universitas Udayana*.
- Yap, Foong Ha, Karen Grunow-Hårsta and Janick Wrona. 2011. Nominalization strategies in Asian languages. In Foong Ha Yap, Karen Grunow-Hårsta and Janick Wrona (eds.), *Nominalization in Asian languages: Diachronic and typological perspectives*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Paul, Ileana. 2014. *Cross-linguistic Investigations of Nominalization Patterns*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Yap, Foong Ha and Hårsta, Karen Grunow. 2010. *Non-Referential Uses of Nominalization Constructions: Asian Perspectives* Hong Kong Polytechnic University. *Language and Linguistics Compass* 3/1 (2010): 1-22, 10.1111/j.1749-818x.2010.00250.x